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Ebf induction by TCF oncogenic network factors in the breast.

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In addition to activation of lymphocyte programs during metastasis (ITK, CD79A/B), induction of the early B-cell factor family EBF1-4 is observed early in transformation of the human breast, together supporting the existence of a transdifferentiation event occurring in the breast involving fusion of a hematopoietic cell type as a common precursor event to breast cancer in humans. We demonstrate here through use of artificial transcriptional networks that Ebf induction in the malignant breast could occur independently of interaction with or contributions from a hematopoietic cell type and only required expression of a select group of TCF oncogenic network factors that together constitute a minimal TCF factor network in human breast cancer.